

SMART ENVIRONMENT: THE INFRASTRUCTURE FOR FUTURE CITY

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Abstract: *This paper is devoted to the issues for arranging infrastructures within smart city concept. Infrastructure by definition is composed of public and private physical structures (roads, railways, bridges, water supply, electrical grids, and telecommunications), thus providing fundamental facilities and services for making country, city or area functional. It is the maintenance and development of infrastructure that makes up the tremendous share of budgets. The term “smart environment” has emerged, which refers to the result of combining physical infrastructure with digital infrastructure, which allows for more information to be provided for management decisions. At the same time, both physical and digital infrastructures are assets for which economic efficiency can and should be considered.*

Keywords: *smart environment, Smart City, IoT, digital infrastructures, Smart Grid, green building, energy efficiency, alternative energy, smart mobility, urban programs, Robotics, Cloud services, BigApp*

Over the past decades, we have seen how accelerating scientific and technological progress changes our way of life beyond recognition, but hardly affect the architectural environment. People live in the same houses and apartments, and newly built houses are often no better than the old ones. But perhaps in the coming years there will be radical transformations of the urban environment under the general banner of a “smart city”, which, in turn, will become a catalyst for even more significant changes in people’s lives.

So-called smart cities use information and communication technologies (ICT) to achieve cost and energy savings, improve service delivery and quality of life, and reduce environmental impact. This can be overviewed by taking a glance at different deployment cases all over the world.

As part of the low-carbon economy promoted in European countries, using technologies such as:

- smart mobility (electric vehicles, unmanned vehicles, ITS – intelligent transport systems, MaaS – “mobility as a service, on demand”);
- smart energy (solar energy, energy saving, Smart Grid - smart energy supply networks);
- smart planning and construction (smart home systems – automation, energy efficiency , BIM – building information modeling, AR/VR – augmented/virtual reality, artificial intelligence), etc.

According to the developers, a smart city uses digital technologies to improve its performance, vitality and well-being of its citizens. New technologies and data are used to solve economic, social and environmental problems of cities. Pilot projects are appearing in significant numbers in the Baltic countries: Finland, Estonia, Latvia; similar plans are also being considered by the administration of other regions.

All smart city programs in the Baltic region are characterized by the introduction of energy-saving street lighting systems, intelligent metering of utility resources, as well as elements of smart mobility. In particular, Gatchina and Sosnovy Bor, according to TASS, should become pilot cities in the Leningrad region in the implementation of the departmental project of the Russian Ministry of Construction “Smart City” [1]. In Gatchina, it is also planned to develop a mobile application for residents, synchronized with the digital portal of the locality, and to create a network of bicycle paths with bicycle parking using modern lighting technologies and light control of traffic. In Sosnovy Bor they are going to modernize the “People's Control” card with the development of a mobile service. The transport infrastructure development plan includes the creation of a unified structure for informing passengers at stops and even the development of a “Unmanned Taxi”. Similar systems have already been implemented or are being tested in many Finnish cities, as well as in the Baltic States.

A feature of some urban programs in Estonia and Latvia is the reconstruction of Soviet panel houses according to modern energy efficiency standards. In some Latvian cities, such as Jelgava (interface is featured in Fig.1), crisis management systems (associated with video surveillance networks, environmental monitoring, etc.), systems for administering social benefits and payments, etc. are being introduced [2].

Fig. 1. Collection of traffic flow data in Jelgava

The SmartEnCity pilot project plans to increase the vitality of the city through smart personal lighting, biogas buses, electric car and bicycle rental, as well as charging stations and various ICT solutions. In addition, it is intended to “involve citizens in creating a quality living environment that inspires environmentally sound decisions and new behavior patterns” [3].

In Finland, the environmental aspect of the smart cities program is even more developed. In particular, the Helsinki development plan involves achieving “carbon neutrality” by 2035. The principles of the “sharing economy” are being actively introduced, for example, in the new Smart district Kalasatama, where people will share cars and parking spaces using digital applications, and Jätkäsaari Smart Mobility Lab and intelligent open data services will save one hour of each citizen’s time per day.

There are networks designed to enable real-time smart metering, electric vehicle networks and new energy storage solutions. Renewable energy sources will be used, in particular in a solar power plant. In the near future, civilian robot buses will appear on the streets of Vallila and Pasila districts. In addition, Helsinki became the first Scandinavian city to create a semantic 3D CityGML model throughout its territory [4].

The city of Tampere is developing an IoT platform for a smart city, implementing a project for managing urban ecosystems and carrying out city development activities within the framework of the STARDUST project. The smart city IoT platform aims to improve the ability of city systems to collect and use data. As for STARDUST, the main idea here is to showcase various “islands of innovation” as urban incubators for technological, social, regulatory and market solutions.

Information technologies are penetrating wider and deeper into the objects and buildings around us, forming the so-called ‘smart environment’. Smart city concepts related to such aspects as network structures, information technology, ecology and green building, energy efficiency and alternative energy, as well as smart mobility, in most cases pursue three main goals, three ‘C’s: comfort, control and commercialization. The developed programs involve increasing the well-being of citizens, on the one hand, control over movement, production, consumption, redistribution, etc., on the other hand, and benefiting from all this, on the third hand. These goals may be in balance, or they may seriously contradict each other.

For modern researchers, different combinations of “C” are possible, except for one: comfort and control without commercialization. This is reminiscent of the words of the actor in Tom Stoppard's play *Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are Dead* (1966): “You know, we rather belong to the school for which the main thing is blood, love and rhetoric ... Well, we can give you blood and love without rhetoric or blood and rhetoric without love; but I cannot give you love and rhetoric without blood. Blood is required, sir...” Just as essential is commerce, without which urbanists cannot imagine a healthy city. However, some designers think differently [5].

Information and communication technologies rely on: M2M telemetry, Internet of Things (IoT), Internet of Everything; technologies for collecting and working with Big Data; Intelligent technologies for working with data (Data visualization technologies); Mobile applications (BigApp) based on open data; Quantum computing; Cloud services and technologies; Blockchain technology; Augmented reality technologies; Cyber-physical systems; Open source software; Geographic information systems based on satellite observations; Video conferencing technologies, telepresence; Electronic services and services; Information modeling of buildings and structures; Engineering and technical developments: Smart grids, Innovative materials, Robotics; Technologies for controlling harmful emissions; Technologies for separate collection and recycling of waste; Water purification technologies, to name some essential.

Prototypes of “smart” cities, implying a balance of various “Cs,” appeared in the middle of the twentieth century. In the early 1960s. French avant-garde sculptor of Hungarian origin Nicolas Schöffer developed the concept of a cybernetic city, which in some aspects anticipated modern ideas of “smart” urban planning. Schöffer extended the principles of “spatial dynamism”, which he applied in kinetic art objects with changing lighting, to the organization of the urban environment, where the movement of individual elements will be controlled by a computer system.

At the same time Soviet architect Vyacheslav Loktev proposed a concept combining “the creation of flexible structures with cybernetic modeling of the city and settlement zone”. The development of the idea of a spatial city was expressed in the design of a vertical system, which “must be organized so that the blocks of each individual network cell can be reconstructed at any time or replaced if necessary” (a related principle is found in the projects of Japanese metabolists).

In 1969, a book by Kenneth S. Keyes Jr. was published and Jacques Fresco's "Looking Ahead" (similar to Edward Bellamy's book "Looking Backward" (1888), which describes the technocratic utopia of the year 2000) [6]. The option of a "cybernetic city" with complete automation of production, transport and management is combined with the ideas of global infrastructure and a resource-based economy, which require a restructuring of the entire world system of social relations, as well as profound changes in human culture.

Today, the implementation of "smart city" systems encounters a number of contradictions: "smart" production calls into question the future of the capitalist economy, "smart" management undermines traditional political institutions, "smart" mobility is effective only if a person is completely removed from driving, etc. The paradoxical combination of carelessness generated by shifting more and more responsibilities to cyber systems, and idea caused by an increasingly greater level of control over people's lives, is shaking the human being. The technological statements so far need to consider such interactions within smart environment, in order to set the appropriate user' experience and better functionality outcomes while leveraging necessary requirement need to be properly elaborated.

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